

The Ocean Pollution Data and Information Network (OPDIN)

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Abstract

The National Ocean Pollution Planning Act of 1978 (Public Law 95-273) designated the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) as the lead agency for coordinating a Federal ocean pollution program. To support Section 8 of this Act, NOAA's National Oceanographic Data Center established in 1981 the Central Coordination and Referral Office, to manage the development and operation of an Ocean Pollution Data and Information Network (OPDIN). The purpose of this Network, as stated in Section 8, is to disseminate, in timely manner and useful forms, the results, findings and information obtained from Federally-sponsored marine pollution programs. The development of an operational Network is being accomplished in a phased manner, in response to interagency workshop recommendations and guidance from potential Network participants. A number of operational activities are already in place. An interagency OPDIN "Round Table" is being formed to serve as an advisory group for further development and implementation strategies to enable the Network to be fully operational before 1985.

Background

Recognizing a need to improve coordination among Federal activities concerned with ocean pollution, Congress enacted in 1978 what is now known as the "National Ocean Pollution Planning Act of 1978" (Public Law 95-273). This Act designates

the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) as the agency for coordinating a Federal ocean pollution program. The Ocean Pollution Data and Information Network (OPDIN) has been established to fulfill Section 8 of that Act, which addresses timely and useful dissemination of ocean pollution data and information resulting from Federally-sponsored programs. In February 1979, NOAA's National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) was assigned the responsibility for the initial development and management of the Network.

To resolve the concerns identified in Section 8 of PL 95-273, an interagency Ocean Pollution Data Collection, Storage and Distribution Subcommittee of the Committee on Ocean Pollution Research and Development and Monitoring (hereafter identified in this paper as COPRDM) was formed. In April 1979, this Subcommittee recommended in a report (COPRDM, 1979) a network approach as a means of facilitating dissemination of ocean pollution data and information.

In May 1981, the Central Coordination and Referral Office (hereafter referred to as CCRO) was established within the NODC to oversee the design and development of an operational OPDIN and to coordinate on-going activities. Related Workshops were held in January 1981 (Hughes, 1981) and May 1982 (CCRO, 1982) to solicit recommendations and comments for implementing the Subcommittee's proposal from both Federal and non-Federal interests in marine pollution data and information. Results

Figure 1. OPDIN Organizational Components (Proposed)

of the workshops and recommendations from potential Network participants provided the proposed framework for the form and initial operating strategy for the Network (Figure 1). Subject-area data centers, proposed by the Subcommittee, were modified somewhat as a result of workshop recommendations, to become Regional Coordination and Referral Offices (RCROs). Initial sites for the RCRO functions were proposed to be the current NODC liaison offices located at Woods Hole, Miami, La Jolla, Seattle and Anchorage.

Current Activities

As specified by the Subcommittee, the Network is being implemented using existing Federal systems and services wherever possible. Thus, the role of the OPDIN is to supplement rather than replace existing agency systems. To that end, much of the Network efforts to date have concentrated on improving communications and exchanging information within NOAA and with other relevant Federal agency networks already in place.

Coordination among Federal marine pollution activities has been enhanced through OPDIN contractor efforts (Electronic Data Systems Corp. [EDS] and EG&G's Washington Analytical Services Center) and cooperation of information system specialists in relevant Federal agencies. These and numerous other Federal personnel are providing a wealth of information concerning their particular systems and services. Contractor visits to both head-quarter and field offices also provided valuable suggestions and guidance concerning future implementation of the Network.

Detailed information on existing systems is being compiled by the OPDIN contractor in the form of an "Investigative Guide", which includes: descriptions of system characteristics; systems users and costs for services; types and quantity of available data and information; access and response time for data retrieval and product generation;

and, principal contacts for each system.

An abbreviated version of this material titled "A Handbook of Federal Systems and Services for Marine Pollution Data and Information" is available in draft form. Descriptions of nearly all Federal agencies identified as having marine pollution-related projects or programs (Figure 2) are represented in this handbook in various formats.

A widely distributed document prepared by Electronic Data Systems Corp. in March 1982 (EDS, 1982a) has been the basis for much of the detailed investigations currently underway by the EG&G contractor team. Other supporting OPDIN documents that have been made available to potential network participants and other interested parties include Network guidelines and scope of marine pollution data and information (CCRO, 1982b), a preliminary network user profile (EG&G, 1983), and an approach to a conceptual design for the Network (EDS, 1982b).

In response to workshop recommendations that development of the Network be pursued in a phased manner, the CCRO has directed a significant amount of resources and contractor efforts in areas that will help satisfy both immediate and future operational Network needs. These areas concern referral, acquisition, processing and quality control, archival, or product dissemination of marine pollution data and information. Major accomplishments to date include the following:

- Establishment of a marine toxic substances and pollutant data system within the NODC marine environmental data base. This system employs a nationally accepted code scheme for identifying chemicals and pollutants (the American Chemical Society's Chemical Abstract Service registration numbers) and also uses NODC's Taxonomic Code system for species identification.

Figure 2. Federal Marine Pollution - Related Agencies

<u>Department/Agency</u>	<u>Subagency/Activity</u>
Agriculture	National Agricultural Library
Commerce	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration National Bureau of Standards National Technical Information Service
Defense	Army Corps of Engineers Navy
Energy	Ecological Research Office Technical Information Center
Health and Human Services	Food and Drug Administration National Institutes of Health
Interior	Minerals Management Service Geological Survey Fish and Wildlife Service
Transportation	Coast Guard
Environmental Protection Agency	Research and Development Programs Environmental Research Laboratories
National Aeronautics and Space Administration	Remote Sensing Technology Program
National Science Foundation	Biological, Chemical, and Physical Programs
Nuclear Regulatory Commission	Environmental Impact Assessment

- Installation of data workstations in each regional NODC liaison office to facilitate marine pollution data entry and edit, and to coordinate CCRO/RCRO management and resource files.
- Completion of a study (AEIDC and NODC, 1983) of state-of-the-art hardware and personnel resources best suited for converting manuscript information to digital data forms. The study examines key entry tasks using data workstations, terminals, microcomputers and voice entry for selected data types employing personnel with either key entry, secretarial or scientific experience. This task was completed through a cooperative agreement between the NODC and the University of Alaska.
- Development of a prototype coastal information system using the latest personal computer capabilities as a tool for regional decision-makers and managers, as well as for Network participants and other local and regional interests. This task is now in the second year of a two-year developmental effort and is part of a cooperative agreement between NOAA and the State University of New York at Stony Brook. An IBM Personal Computer is being used to provide information on both space-specific (shorelines, rivers, water areas, etc.) and use-specific interests (fisheries, marine transportation, waste disposal, etc.). General information files including glossary of terms, map and chart index, and a reference file for all data entered in the system also are available.
- Identification of potential data files for inclusion in NOAA's National Environmental Data Referral Service (NEDRES). Files are being identified through the efforts of both the regional NODC liaison offices and by OPDIN contractors during their existing systems investigations.
- Completion of the annual update of the National Marine Pollution Information System (NMPIS), an automated data base used to generate a catalog of Federal marine pollution programs and projects (COPRDM, 1982). The information system also provides valuable support for the Federal Plan (COPRDM, 1981) prepared periodically by NOAA's National Marine Pollution Program Office. The automated data base also serves the CCRO as a primary source of information for requests concerning Federal program and project activities.
- Support for the "Coastal Ocean Pollution Assessment News", a newsletter jointly funded by OPDIN and three other NOAA offices with coastal pollution interests. The newsletter, produced quarterly since the fall of 1980, concentrates on society's impacts on the coastal regions of the United States, including the Great Lakes. Specific topics include: quality of coastal waters; impacts of pollution on public health and living resources; programs that assess society's impacts; and, efforts underway to manage and rehabilitate coastal waters.

While accomplishing the above tasks, the CCRO also has been involved in responding to a number of data and information requests from Federal and state offices as well as university and private industry sources. Requests have been primarily

for OPDIN materials, products generated from the NMPIS, and retrievals of pollution-related data from the NODC archives.

Future Efforts

One of the more important conceptual design components endorsed by the OPDIN Planning Workshop (CCRO, 1982) is the establishment of an OPDIN "Round Table". This "Round Table" is intended to serve as an interagency advisory group for OPDIN development and implementation tasks. The group also would provide guidance and priorities for future efforts in response to the data and information needs of the marine pollution community. Invitations to become members of the "Round Table" were issued earlier this year to members of the COPRDM and its Task Force group. Specific individuals from principal Federal agencies are now being identified to serve on the "Round Table". The first meeting of the group is planned to be held before the end of the calendar year, when detailed design elements and investigative guide materials will be subject to review and evaluation.

While operational tasks are underway, detailed system design and implementation plans continue to be developed in coordination with OPDIN contractor findings, and evaluations and support from the NODC's Systems Planning and Integration staff. As Network objectives and requirements are more specifically defined, and detailed investigative guide material and additional user profile information from potential Network participants is analyzed, a detailed system design will be made available for Network participant and Round Table review. From this close interaction within NOAA and with other Federal offices, it is anticipated that the resulting network design will meet both current and future needs for improved data and information dissemination to the marine pollution user community.

In addition to completing the detailed system design and continuing to work on many of the ongoing tasks described above, 1984 CCRO interests will also focus on a number of other activities, some of which directly affect future Network operations. Major efforts during 1984 plan to include:

- Participation in the NOAA Quality Assurance Program for marine chemistry and pollutant measurements;
- Coordination with other NOAA offices concerning the agency's role in marine estuaries and wetlands;
- Cooperation with NOAA offices involved in surveys and the assessment of non-Federal activities in marine pollution monitoring, research and development;
- More direct involvement in the efforts to include new and updated descriptions of marine pollution-related data bases in NOAA's National Environmental Data Referral System;
- Generation of Federal marine pollution program awareness reports or specific pollutant categories or regional activities using the National Marine Pollution Information System data base;

- ° Publication and distribution of a final version of the handbook for Federal systems and services;
- ° Automation of "Investigative Guide" material to be used as a major CCRO/RCRO resource file for timely access and referral to agency sources of marine pollution data and information;
- ° Investigation of the feasibility of transferring the prototype coastal information system technology and methodology to other estuaries and regional areas of interest;
- ° Utilization of the findings of the data entry evaluation study to capture selected marine pollution data from regional sources in a cost-effective and timely manner; and,
- ° Further improvements in the NODC marine toxic substances data system, including conversion of associated digital data files to that system for easier access and retrieval of specific pollutant data.

In terms of marketing of current and planned OPDIN capabilities, this effort will be accelerated in 1984, principally through the distribution of NODC fliers and announcements that describe OPDIN products, providing new OPDIN materials to regional offices (RCROs) for distribution within their regions, informing readers of OPDIN progress in contributions to COPAS and similar newsletters, and participation in interagency and regional meetings and workshops.

Conclusion

It is anticipated that with continued cooperation of the different Federal agencies and with contractor support, the Network will attain before 1985, through a phased implementation approach, a fully operational status, as perceived when the original goals and milestones were developed in 1981.

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